

CARE OF HOUSE PLANTS. TECHNOLOGY OF GROWING FLOWERS BY PLANTATION

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Abstract. *In this article, natural, indoor plant care and flower planting technology. Also, choosing the most suitable technologies depending on the type of flowers and the conditions of the room. This article analyzes when and how to use houseplant care technologies to create a good environment for plant care.*

Keywords: *indoor flowers, plants, mineral and local fertilizers, transplanting, loosening the soil layer, plant nutrition, aloe, sansevieria, Ficus Benjamin, aloe vera.*

INTRODUCTION

Elementary school students are engaged in the maintenance and cultivation of classroom flowers and indoor plants in labor lessons. They consist of:

- cleaning plant dust;
- loosening the soil layer;
- watering plants with water;
- feeding with mineral and local nutrients;
- growing plants as seedlings;
- monitor the growth and development of plants.

Every office has indoor flowers and plants. They also serve as the appearance and decoration of the room. But few people know that in addition to beauty, indoor plants are a real source of oxygen. A plant is a living thing and lives because it breathes. In fact, there are plants that emit oxygen even at night. For humans, this is a great benefit: nervousness, anxiety is reduced, and the risk of insomnia is reduced. Scientists recommend buying one of the 10 plants on this list. It is they who release oxygen both day and night.

1. Aloe vera.

This unique plant should be in every office! Aloe juice helps in the treatment of any disease, especially known for its antiseptic properties.

The plant is the leader among others in terms of the amount of oxygen released at night. In addition, the plant is not capricious and does not need special care. To maximize the effect of the plant, you can place it in every room of your office.

2. Sansevieria

The name of this houseplant sounds like something scary, but it contains many positive qualities. So, "Sansevieria" should be in every office.

This is one of the best natural air purifiers. And like aloe vera, it does not require complex conditions for its life and growth and requires minimal care - watering depends on the dryness of the soil. An ideal choice, especially for those who do not like to take care of indoor plants.

3. Nim (India Azadirachta)

Neem (Indian Azadirachta) is its second name - the plant of purity.

Indian scientists have noticed the special properties of this plant for a long time. It not only cleans the air, but also acts as a natural pesticide, creating a barrier between you and pesky

mosquitoes and gnats. In fact, it not only kills pests, but also destroys them, prevents the spread of new insects by preventing them from laying larvae.

The only disadvantage of a natural vacuum cleaner is high-quality soil and a lot of sunlight.

4. Tulasi

This plant is valued not only for its taste, but also for its aroma. Its leaves emit a very characteristic smell that has a beneficial effect on the human nervous system. Inhaling its aroma reduces anxiety and nervousness. In other words, tula has a soothing and calming effect, thereby helping a person to relax and restore mental peace. Especially for nervous people, this plant becomes a preventive tool in the treatment and prevention of psychosis.

5. Orchid

A real decoration for any room. Its beauty cannot be compared with other indoor plants. In addition to aesthetic satisfaction, it emits a lot of oxygen, so it is better to place the flower in rooms. In addition, they clean the air from xylene, which is a harmful pollutant contained in various paints. In other words, thanks to the orchid, your room will be clean, fresh, and it will be easier to breathe deeply. Careful care and the myth that the orchid is a capricious plant is nonsense. Normal watering and enough solar energy are enough. So, even if you are an inexperienced gardener, this does not prevent you from having an orchid in your room.

6. Orange gerbera

Undoubtedly, beautiful flowers purify the air and cure many diseases at the same time. The benefits of orange gerbera are as follows: they cure colds and also prevent cancer. It should be noted that this flower absorbs toxic substances such as benzene. Gerbera promotes healthy and quality sleep; it absorbs carbon dioxide emitted by a person and releases oxygen instead. They are strange in transplanting and growing, but if you really appreciate its beneficial qualities for human health, it is worth it.

7. Ficus Benjamin

The beneficial properties of this plant are clear. Ficus is a powerful source of oxygen, and the leaves of this plant are also used to treat diabetes, prevent constipation, and treat asthma.

8. Christmas cactus (Decemberist)

It blooms only in December, but benefits all year round!

Cactus also releases oxygen at night, contributes to healthy and sound sleep, and fills the room with oxygen. It grows well in dark rooms, which is ideal for your room.

9. Plants of the palm family

It is a versatile plant and is often found in the corridors of hospitals and offices. This plant perfectly cleans the air from harmful impurities and gases, as well as moistens it and fills it with useful trace elements. They are not whimsical, they grow mainly in dark places, because they do not like sunlight very much.

10. Kalanchoe

This flower, in addition to its amazing beauty and attractiveness, is also distinguished by the fact that it has unique useful properties. For Kalanchoe to grow and bloom well, it is very important to have plenty of water and bright sunlight. It should be remembered that this plant fills the air with oxygen both during the day and at night. It is known that the smell of Kalanchoe effectively fights depression, bad mood and sleep problems.

Choosing a container for houseplants: Ceramic pots are the best container for houseplants. Their walls are porous, and air (oxygen) passes well to plant roots. Wooden containers can also be used. Plastic pots are for some humidity-loving flowers

or used to send flowers from one place to another. Do not use metal and enameled dishes. Because over time, these containers emit various substances that change the composition of the radish (they rust). Before planting plants in old flower beds, it is necessary to wash them with soap and water in boiling water. This situation is necessary in order not to infect newly planted plants with any disease.

Transplantation and transplanting of plants: As a result of the gradual assimilation of nutrients and mineral substances dissolved in water in the soil through plant roots, the soil becomes weak. In order to improve the nutrition of plants, their content is periodically transferred to new soil. The plant is transplanted only if it does not grow well, the leaves begin to wither, and the roots cover the entire soil or small roots form a patch.

Transplantation of plants: Before transplanting the plant, the soil in the pot is watered until it is all wet. After the plant is removed from the pot with its soil, it is determined whether it needs to be transplanted. If there is no need to transplant, the plant knocked out of the pot is transplanted into a slightly larger (2-3 cm) pot with soil and a little soil is added. Even if the plant is moved during the flowering period, there will be no change. The size of the soil or soil in which the plant is transplanted should not be too different from the previous one. Don't forget! flowering or diseased plants are not transplanted. They can only be moved.

Transplantation of plants: Plants are mainly transplanted in early spring (March-April). Diseased and flowering plants are not transplanted. At the bottom of small pots, spoons, expanded clay, pieces of pebbles or small stones are placed. In this case, the soil does not cover the water hole at the bottom of the tub. When the plant is transplanted, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the root neck is equal to the surface of the soil. After the plant is transplanted, the soil around the stem is pressed with a stick or index finger, and the edges of the pot are left free for watering. Then the plant is watered and sprayed with water, placed in a warm place away from wind and sunlight. Don't forget! flowering or diseased plants are not transplanted. They can only be moved.

Propagation of plants: House plants are propagated from seeds or cuttings (stems, leaves, or roots), root pieces, nodules, bulbs, bulbs, and rhizomes. At home, vegetative propagation (rather than sowing) from its own parts is more often used, because it is possible to create a mature plant in a short time and keep the variety clean. Cuttings are cut from young, healthy and well-developed plants with 1-3 young branches, sometimes with many leaves, obliquely below the joint. In order to reduce evaporation, 1-2 leaves or half of the leaves are cut off from the cuttings, then they are planted on the surface of soft soil consisting of leaf humus and a mixture of humus and sand, and the soil is well pressed around it.

How to care for houseplants so that their leaves do not turn yellow?

Especially in the case of flowers grown at home in the winter season, sooner or later their leaves often turn yellow. So something may be going wrong with care. This can be defined as:

Too much or too little watering: Usually the top layer of soil dries out faster. As a result, the plants seem to be without water. In fact, it is not so. In order to determine the moisture content of the soil, it is necessary to insert a finger into the soil 2-3 centimeters deeper. It is also necessary to carry out this inspection during regular watering of plants. If the soil, on the other hand, is too wet, it is necessary to check the roots of the plants. The reason may be that they were damaged by excessive watering, and signs of rot appeared. In such a situation, it is necessary to transfer the plant to another pot and protect it from wilting. Also, the above instruction regarding watering is recommended.

Check for pests. If watering is carried out regularly, then the reason for the yellowing of the leaves may be pests. The most common of them are the white-winged fly and the spider mite. Sometimes it is difficult to identify them immediately, so it is necessary to carefully examine the

leaves. If there are small holes or white dots on the leaves, as well as a web like a spider's web, then there are pests. They feel great at room temperature. To eliminate them, the plant leaf should be thoroughly washed. For this, you can use laundry soap or dishwashing detergent. After that, they need to use special preparations from the group of acaricide and insectocicide. If you need to use only natural products at home, then "Nim" oil can help.

Sunlight falling on plants. Another reason for yellowing leaves is lack of sunlight. Of course, this is more common in autumn and winter. If all the windows are facing away from the sun, the plants will suffer. Therefore, it is necessary to place plants near the window or organize artificial lighting. The lack of light is reflected first of all in the lower part of the plant. They turn yellow and begin to fade.

Protection from wind. Most of the houseplants are typical of natural tropical countries, they are not resistant to cold and wind. That's why you shouldn't be surprised if the plant turns yellow standing in front of a slightly open window. Also, if the plant is in a cool room, watering should be reduced. By the way, plants can freeze not only in the cold season, but also under a constantly running air conditioner. Due to the lack of nitrogen fertilizer, the old leaves turn yellow, and the new ones remain green. Therefore, it is necessary not to forget to add nitrogen fertilizer in moderation. Excess can harm them again.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that elementary school students are engaged in the care and cultivation of flowers and indoor plants in the classroom during labor lessons. Ceramic pots are the best containers for house plants. Their walls are porous, and air (oxygen) passes well to plant roots. In order to improve the nutrition of plants, their content is periodically transferred to new soil. Plants are mainly transplanted in early spring (March-April). Diseased and flowering plants are not transplanted.

REFERENCES

1. Sanakulov H.R., Khodiyeva D.P. Satbayeva "Methodology of labor and its teaching". Study guide. T.: TDPU. 2015.

2. M. Tilavova "Technology and its teaching methodology". Study guide. "Durdona" publishing house. Bukhara-2021
3. S. Yoldashov "Technology and its teaching methodology". Textbook. Tashkent-2021.